

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH MALONIC ACID.
PART XVII. CONDENSATION OF *p*-DIMETHYL-
AMINOBENZALDEHYDE

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The influence of the amino group has been investigated in the aldehyde-malonic acid condensation. The expected inhibitive character is seen. With *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, no condensation is found to take place by the usual method of the 0.15 mol. of pyridine under various conditions. Use of excess of pyridine, up to three mols. gives a poor yield. With a trace of piperidine, however, the yield rises to 55% which increases still further when a pyridine-piperidine mixture is used, the highest yield of about 80% is obtained by applying Vorsatz's method. The related dibasic acid cannot be isolated in spite of several attempts, which again points to the inhibitive character of the group.

The previous parts of this series have been concerned with the investigation, not only of the influence of pyridine and other bases on the aldehyde-malonic acid condensation, but also of the influence of various groups occurring on the ring of the aromatic aldehyde on the same condensation. In this way the hydroxy and, to some extent, the methyl groups are found to be decreasing the yield, and the methoxy, the methylene-dioxy, the nitro, the chloro and the bromo groups are found to be, more or less, increasing the yields of the condensation products. In fact, the reactions,

(where R=Ph), are tremendously influenced, not only by the ordinary conditions of the reaction (such as the temperature at which the reaction is carried out, the time of keeping or heating, the presence or the absence of organic bases like pyridine], but also by the nature of the group or groups, and their position and number, that may be present in the ring. This influence is clearly marked on the speed of the reactions, on the yield of the condensation product and, to an extent, on its purity.

The amino group has not so far been included, either in this survey of the aldehyde-malonic acid condensation or in that of Perkin's reaction (Lock and Bayer, *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1064). One possible reason is the greater difficulty of preparing the aminobenzaldehydes in a pure condition, and the other is certainly the alleged inhibitive nature of the amino group itself.

The condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde has been studied in this paper. Weil (*Monatsh.*, 1908, 29, 895) reports that *p*-dimethylaminocinnamic acid may be obtained by using the Perkin's reaction with the aldehyde, preferably when potassium acetate is used in place of sodium acetate in the condensation. Meyer and Beer (*ibid.*, 1913, 34, 649) confirm this, adding that the reaction takes place only in the presence of potassium acetate, and not in the presence of sodium acetate. Thoms and Seebe (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1926, 39, 1496) have concluded that the introduction of the *p*-dimethylamino group reduces the reactivity of benzaldehyde in cinnamic acid synthesis and causes a tendency to give by-products. Hinkel and Cremer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 137) also report on its retarding effect, as expected, in Hantzsch's pyridine synthesis.

The expected difficulty was realised in the present condensation; no condensation product was obtained in the usual water-bath condensation with a small trace of pyridine (1 : 1 : 0.15 mol.). Increase in the period of heating or decrease in the temperature of the water-bath down to 60°, when the reactants became a homogeneous liquid, effected no improvement. Increase in the amount of malonic acid gave no yield, resinification often taking place and much of the aldehyde being recovered unchanged. Absolute alcohol and absolute alcohol with hydrochloric acid were used to check resin-formation, together with a trace of pyridine; a yellow turbid solution was obtained, suggesting some condensation, but no solid could be separated. More of pyridine was used; with one mol. of pyridine, about 2% of the expected product came out; with 3 mols., 5.3% came out. Piperidine was then substituted, and then the yield went up to 55%. Robinson and Shinoda's pyridine-piperidine mixture and refluxing on a wire-gauze (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1977), gave 60% yield. A pyridine-piperidine mixture (1 : 1 : 3 : a few drops) gave on 8 hours' heating on a water-bath 73.3% yield. The best yield was obtained by following Vorsatz's method (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1936, 145, 265) by keeping the mixture (1 : 2 : 6 : 0.15) at room temperature for three weeks, when the yield rose to over 79% (*vide* Experimental).

While the difficulty in the condensation was overcome by various means, the condensation that should produce the undecarboxylated dibasic acid did not meet with equal success. All possible methods were tried but *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenemalonic acid could not be isolated; much resin and unchanged aldehyde were generally obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation in the presence of Pyridine.—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.75 g.), malonic acid (0.52 g.) and pyridine (0.07 c.c.) (1 : 1 : 0.15 mol.) were heated together on a water-bath. In three minutes the whole mixture became a homogeneous liquid and within ten minutes effervescence started, the colour becoming green soon after. But the colour rapidly changed to greenish yellow, brown and ultimately dark red. Effervescence stopped after two hours but no solidification took place. After 5 hours' heating the mixture was cooled overnight. Reddish resinous material when treated with sodium carbonate solution gave a brown precipitate, which was found to be the unchanged aldehyde. The alkali extract gave nothing on acidification. The aldehyde recovered was about 0.5 g. It appears as if the effervescence was due only to the breaking down of the malonic acid.

Three more experiments with slight alterations, such as heating for 8 hours on a water-bath, with 2 mols. of malonic acid, and heating at 60° with 3 mols. of malonic acid, did not bring about any change in the result. In the next experiment absolute alcohol was taken also (1 : 1 : 15 : 0.15 mols.) and the heating was done on a water-bath with a reflux condenser for 5 hours. A yellow turbid solution was obtained, suggesting that a slight reaction had taken place. The same experiment was repeated with the addition of 1 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The result was the same.

Larger amounts of pyridine effected the condensation. Thus with a molecular proportion of pyridine (1 : 1 : 1 mol.), a little yellow precipitate came out, melting at 211° and identifiable with the expected *p*-dimethylaminocinnamic acid, yield 2% of theory. With 3 mols. of pyridine for one of the aldehyde and one of the acid, the yield was 5.3%. The product melted at 212° with decomposition.

Condensation in the presence of Piperidine.—With a trace of piperidine the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 5 hours. Effervescence commenced in 10 minutes and the colour became blood-red. After an hour a solid began to separate, and complete solidification was apparent in 2 hours. The heating was stopped after 5 hours and the flask was left overnight. The beautiful red solid mass was treated as usual, the unused aldehyde was removed with ether, and the bright yellow precipitate, obtained on acidifying the sodium salt extract, was filtered, dried and recrystallised from alcohol, the final m.p. was 216°, yield 55%. Increase in the amount of piperidine by doubling it brought no increase in the yield, but the additional use of absolute alcohol as before gave the yield up to 62.8%.

Condensation in the presence of Pyridine-piperidine Mixture.—Reactants in the molecular proportion [1 : 1 : 3 (pyridine) : 0.15] were heated on a water-bath for 8 hours : the yield was 73.3%.

Robsinson and Shinoda's method (*loc. cit.*) gave 60% yield. While Vorsatz's method (*loc. cit.*) gave the best yield of 79.6% of theory (0.75 g. aldehyde, 1.0 g. acid, 2.4 c.c. pyridine and 0.05 c.c. piperidine, at room temperature, 10-21° for 3 weeks.)

Condensation in the presence of Sodium Ethoxide.—The aldehyde (0.75 g.), malonic acid (0.5 g.) were added to a mixture of 0.04 g. sodium in 3 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The well-corked flask was kept aside for 6 weeks. After one week a little yellow crystalline

product began to separate. The product, taken out^a after six weeks, was almost pure, but the yield was only about 16%.

The identity of all the products was established not only by identical m.p., but by the mixed m.p. also, which remained unchanged. The equivalent weight was found by titration against baryta as well as sodium hydroxide. (Found : N, 7.56 ; equiv., 189.5, 190.5. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 7.33 per cent. Equiv., 191). The acid crystallised from alcohol in yellow shining leaflets. Its colour deepens at 205°, becoming perfectly brown at 210°. Shrinking starts at 213°, while complete melting takes place at 216°, with great effervescence and colour changing to dark red. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, a little less in acetone, chloroform and benzene, and is almost insoluble in water and ether. It readily decolourises bromine water and Baeyer's reagent in the cold. Its amphoteric character is seen in its easy solubility in alkalis as well as in inorganic acids. With silver nitrate it gives a curdy yellow precipitate of the silver salt.

Attempted preparation of p-Dimethylaminobenzylidenemalonic Acid.—Every experiment devised for this purpose failed ; in most of them almost the whole of the aldehyde was recovered unchanged. The experiments composed in heating on the water-bath alone the aldehyde and the malonic acid in molecular proportions, at different temperatures of water-bath, heating with strong and glacial acetic acid, with absolute alcohol, with acetic anhydride, and in an inert atmosphere (nitrogen). In cases where the recovered aldehyde was less, resinification had already taken place.

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